

A Comparative Study of Sensory and Motor Peripheral Nerve Functions in Elderly Patients of Diabetes Mellitus and Non-Diabetic Control in a Tertiary Care Hospital

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Abstract:

Background: Peripheral neuropathy is a common complication in elderly patients with diabetes mellitus, affecting both sensory and motor nerve functions. Understanding the extent and nature of these dysfunctions can aid in better clinical management and improve quality of life.

Aim: This study aims to compare sensory and motor peripheral nerve functions between elderly diabetic patients and non-diabetic controls in a tertiary care hospital.

Methods A comparative cross-sectional study was conducted to evaluate sensory and motor peripheral nerve functions in 90 elderly diabetic patients and 90 non-diabetic controls. Participants were selected based on strict inclusion and exclusion criteria to minimize bias. Data collection included clinical examinations and electrophysiological studies.

Results: The study of 180 participants revealed significant impairments in sensory and motor nerve functions in diabetic patients. Diabetic patients had reduced vibration sense (8.5 ± 2.1 vs. 12.3 ± 1.8 seconds, $p < 0.001$), higher pinprick sensation scores (2.4 ± 0.6 vs. 1.2 ± 0.3 , $p < 0.001$), lower muscle strength (3.8 ± 0.7 vs. 4.5 ± 0.4 , $p < 0.001$), and abnormal electrophysiological parameters, including reduced motor and sensory nerve conduction velocities (38.2 ± 3.5 vs. 52.1 ± 4.2 m/s and 41.8 ± 3.2 vs. 54.7 ± 4.1 m/s, $p < 0.001$) and increased latencies (4.7 ± 0.6 vs. 3.1 ± 0.4 ms and 3.9 ± 0.5 vs. 2.5 ± 0.3 ms, $p < 0.001$). These results indicate significant peripheral neuropathy in elderly diabetic patients.

Conclusion: Elderly patients with diabetes mellitus exhibit greater impairment in peripheral nerve functions compared to non-diabetic controls. Sensory nerves are more susceptible to dysfunction than motor nerves in diabetic patients.

Recommendations: Regular screening for peripheral neuropathy should be integrated into the routine management of elderly diabetic patients. Early detection and intervention can help mitigate the progression of nerve damage and improve patient outcomes.

Keywords: Peripheral Neuropathy, Diabetes Mellitus, Elderly Patients, Sensory Nerve Function, Motor Nerve Function.

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Introduction

Peripheral neuropathy is a debilitating condition characterized by damage to the peripheral nerves, which can lead to a range of symptoms including pain, numbness, and muscle weakness. It is particularly prevalent among elderly individuals, especially those suffering from chronic conditions such as diabetes mellitus. Diabetes is a major public health concern, known for its numerous complications, including significant impacts on the nervous system. Understanding the extent of peripheral nerve damage in diabetic patients

compared to non-diabetic individuals can provide insights into the management and prevention of this condition [1].

Diabetes mellitus, a metabolic disorder characterized by chronic hyperglycemia, is known to cause microvascular complications that can lead to peripheral neuropathy. This neuropathy can affect both sensory and motor nerves, leading to decreased quality of life and increased morbidity in affected individuals. Sensory nerve dysfunction can manifest as numbness, tingling, and pain, while

motor nerve involvement can lead to muscle weakness and atrophy. These symptoms significantly impair the daily functioning and independence of elderly patients [2].

Non-diabetic elderly individuals can also experience peripheral neuropathy due to age-related changes in nerve function, but the prevalence and severity are generally lower compared to diabetic patients. Factors such as comorbidities, nutritional deficiencies, and lifestyle can also contribute to the development of neuropathy in this population. Comparative studies focusing on diabetic and non-diabetic populations can help delineate the specific impact of diabetes on nerve function, thereby aiding in targeted interventions [3, 4]

The aim of this study is to compare sensory and motor peripheral nerve functions between elderly diabetic patients and non-diabetic controls in a tertiary care hospital. By using nerve conduction studies (NCS), we intend to objectively measure nerve conduction velocity, amplitude, and latency to identify significant differences between the two groups. Peripheral neuropathy poses a significant challenge in the management of elderly patients, particularly those with diabetes mellitus. This study seeks to provide a detailed comparison of nerve function between diabetic and non-diabetic elderly individuals, emphasizing the importance of early detection and intervention. By identifying the specific characteristics and extent of nerve dysfunction in diabetic patients, healthcare providers can better tailor their therapeutic approaches to improve patient outcomes and quality of life.

Methodology

Study Design: A comparative cross-sectional study was conducted to evaluate sensory and motor peripheral nerve functions in elderly patients with diabetes mellitus and non-diabetic controls.

Study Setting: The study was carried out at E. S. I. C. M. C. H., Bihta, Patna over a period of one year.

Participants: A total of 180 participants were included in the study, with 90 diabetic patients and 90 non-diabetic controls. The participants were selected using a purposive sampling technique.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion criteria for diabetic patients were:

- Age 60 years and above.
- Diagnosed with diabetes mellitus for at least 5 years.
- Able to give informed consent.

Inclusion criteria for non-diabetic controls were:

- Age 60 years and above.

- No history of diabetes mellitus.
- Able to give informed consent.

Exclusion criteria for both groups included:

- History of peripheral neuropathy from other causes (e.g., alcoholism, vitamin deficiencies)
- Chronic kidney disease.
- Severe cardiovascular conditions.
- Cognitive impairments preventing participation.

Bias: Selection bias was minimized by using strict inclusion and exclusion criteria. Measurement bias was reduced by standardizing the procedures for nerve function assessment and by blinding the investigators to the group allocation of participants during testing.

Variables: The primary variables were sensory and motor nerve functions, assessed through clinical and electrophysiological tests.

Data Collection: Data were collected using a structured questionnaire to gather demographic and clinical information. Sensory and motor nerve functions were assessed using:

- Clinical examinations (e.g., vibration sense, pinprick sensation)
- Electrophysiological studies (e.g., nerve conduction studies)

Procedure

Participants underwent a thorough clinical examination, including:

1. Assessment of sensory functions: vibration sense using a tuning fork, pinprick sensation using a neurotip.
2. Assessment of motor functions: muscle strength testing using the Medical Research Council (MRC) scale.
3. Electrophysiological studies were performed to measure nerve conduction velocities, amplitudes, and latencies in both upper and lower limbs.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 21.0.

Results

Participant Demographics: The study included 180 participants, with 90 diabetic patients and 90 non-diabetic controls. The mean age of diabetic patients was 67.4 ± 5.2 years, and the mean age of non-diabetic controls was 66.8 ± 5.5 years. There was no significant difference in age between the two groups ($p = 0.58$). The male-to-female ratio was 1.2:1 in both groups.

Sensory Nerve Function: The assessment of sensory nerve function showed significant

differences between diabetic patients and non-diabetic controls.

Table 1: Sensory Nerve Function Assessment

Parameter	Diabetic Patients (Mean ± SD)	Non-Diabetic Controls (Mean ± SD)	p-value
Vibration Sense (seconds)	8.5 ± 2.1	12.3 ± 1.8	<0.001
Pinprick Sensation (score)	2.4 ± 0.6	1.2 ± 0.3	<0.001

Diabetic patients had significantly reduced vibration sense and increased pinprick sensation scores compared to non-diabetic controls ($p < 0.001$ for both).

Motor Nerve Function: Motor nerve function assessment also revealed noteworthy differences between the groups.

Table 2: Motor Nerve Function Assessment

Parameter	Diabetic Patients (Mean ± SD)	Non-Diabetic Controls (Mean ± SD)	p-value
Muscle Strength (MRC)	3.8 ± 0.7	4.5 ± 0.4	<0.001

Diabetic patients exhibited significantly lower muscle strength compared to non-diabetic controls ($p < 0.001$).

clinical findings, showing significant differences in nerve conduction parameters between diabetic patients and non-diabetic controls.

Electrophysiological Studies: The electrophysiological studies further supported the

Table 3: Electrophysiological Study Results

Parameter	Diabetic Patients (Mean ± SD)	Non-Diabetic Controls (Mean ± SD)	p-value
Motor Nerve Conduction Velocity (m/s)	38.2 ± 3.5	52.1 ± 4.2	<0.001
Sensory Nerve Conduction Velocity (m/s)	41.8 ± 3.2	54.7 ± 4.1	<0.001
Motor Nerve Latency (ms)	4.7 ± 0.6	3.1 ± 0.4	<0.001
Sensory Nerve Latency (ms)	3.9 ± 0.5	2.5 ± 0.3	<0.001

Diabetic patients had significantly reduced motor and sensory nerve conduction velocities and increased latencies compared to non-diabetic controls ($p < 0.001$ for all parameters).

Diabetic patients in our study exhibited significantly reduced vibration sense and higher pinprick sensation scores compared to non-diabetic controls. This finding is supported by Dharmendra Kumar et al. (2022), who found that elderly diabetic patients had higher impairment in vibration perception threshold and monofilament tests, indicating a significant sensory deficit [5].

The study found significant impairments in both sensory and motor peripheral nerve functions in elderly diabetic patients compared to non-diabetic controls. Diabetic patients showed reduced vibration sense, increased pinprick sensation scores, lower muscle strength, and abnormal electrophysiological parameters, indicating peripheral neuropathy. These findings highlight the need for regular neurological assessments in elderly diabetic patients to manage and mitigate the progression of neuropathy effectively.

Our study also identified reduced muscle strength and abnormal electrophysiological parameters in diabetic patients. The electrophysiological studies showed reduced motor and sensory nerve conduction velocities and increased latencies, consistent with findings by Shabeeb et al. (2018) who highlighted the importance of electrophysiological examinations in diagnosing diabetic neuropathy due to their accuracy and reliability [6].

Discussion

This study evaluated sensory and motor peripheral nerve functions in elderly diabetic patients with non-diabetic controls, revealing significant impairments in diabetic individuals. Our findings align with several recent studies that have highlighted the prevalence and severity of diabetic neuropathy.

Doshi et al. (2020) found that chronic kidney disease exacerbates sensorimotor nerve impairments, indicating a higher risk for individuals with multiple chronic conditions [7]. This supports our observation that diabetic patients, often having other comorbidities, are more prone to severe neuropathy.

Peripheral nerve impairments have broader implications beyond neuropathy. Brenowitz et al. (2022) indicated that sensory nerve impairments are associated with a higher risk of dementia, suggesting that comprehensive management of diabetic patients should also consider cognitive health [8]. This is particularly relevant given the aging population of diabetic patients.

Conclusion

Our study confirms significant sensory and motor peripheral nerve impairments in elderly diabetic patients compared to non-diabetic controls. These findings underscore the importance of regular neurological assessments and comprehensive management strategies, including lifestyle interventions like resistance training, to address the multifaceted impacts of diabetic neuropathy.

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